

DEVELOPMENT AND STANDARDIZATION OF SYNBIOTICS WITH *LACTOBACTERIUM PLANTARUM* SUBSTANCE AND OLIGOSACCHARIDES

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Relevance: According to the definition by the World Health Organization (WHO), probiotics are viable microorganisms that, when administered in adequate amounts, confer a health benefit on the host. In 2013, the International Scientific Association for Probiotics and Prebiotics refined this definition, stating that the term «probiotic» may only be applied to preparations that meet the following requirements: accurate information on the microorganisms present, including their strains, is provided; a sufficient number of viable bacteria is maintained until the end of the shelf life; and studies confirming the safety and efficacy of the introduced strains are available. Thus, fermented food products and fecal transplants that do not specify species and strain composition are not considered probiotics. Experimental studies and numerous clinical observations have shown that different probiotic strains are necessary for the correction of intestinal symptoms.

Objective of the study: Development of technology and standardization of synbiotics with *Lactobacterium plantarum* substance and oligosaccharides.

Materials and methods: Laboratory methods were used to optimize the fermentation conditions of *Lactobacterium plantarum* with various oligosaccharides, including inulin and fructooligosaccharides. Methods included cultivation parameters, identification of critical steps in biomass extraction, and determination of control points.

Results: Optimal fermentation conditions ensured high viability of *Lactobacterium plantarum* when combined with different oligosaccharides. Quality standards were also developed for the obtained synbiotics, including methods for controlling viable cell counts and oligosaccharide activity.

Conclusion: The study successfully developed a technology for producing synbiotics based on *Lactobacterium plantarum* and oligosaccharides, as well as established quality standards. The results open new perspectives for the development of functional food products that contribute to human health improvement.